

Impact of Field Trip on Academic Performance of Technical Education Students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South- South Nigeria

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Abstract

Technical Education has been recognised as a tool for empowering people especially youths, for sustainable livelihood and social economic development. This study is set to investigate the impact of fieldtrip on the academic performance of technical education students in colleges of education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study while three hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey design was adopted in the study. The population of the study consisted of all staff and students of School of Secondary Education (Technical) in two Federal Colleges of Education (Technical). The entire population of 190 lecturers and students was also used as sample for the study. A four point rating questionnaire titled "Impact of Field Trip on Academic Performance of Technical Education Students Questionnaire (IFTAPTESQ)" was used as instrument for data collection and it was validated by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha which yielded 0.90. Data was analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed among others, that field trip impacted on the academic performance of technical education students. Also, field trip offered quality skills to technical education students. Based on the findings, it was recommended that regular and well planned field trip should be organised for technical education students so as to enable them gain first hand information and provide opportunity for them to see, touch and feel those things that were taught in the classroom. This will enhance their academic performance.

Keywords: Field Trip, Academic Performance, Technical Education, Colleges of Education.

Introduction

Human civilization is quite often linked to technological advances and developments. Skills and knowledge are the engines of technological growth, economic growth and social development of any nation (Goel, 2010). The educational process equips individuals with the relevant knowledge, skills and character for purposeful living in a society. Technical education is recognized as the aspect of education that transfers quality skills into people for a country's technological, economic, social and cultural development (Afeti, 2010). UNESCO (2010) defined technical education as that aspect of educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Amasuomo (2014) viewed technical education as an instrument of technological advancement and industrialization. Amasuomo also reported that the key manpower needed for the rapid development of a nation is technical in nature. Thus, technical education can be regarded as a means of preparing individuals for occupational fields and effective participation in the world of work. This means that the main feature of technical education is its orientation towards the world of work and the curriculum's emphasis is on the acquisition of practical skills. This further implies that the acquisition of practical skills that will provide the technical manpower needed for a country to advance technologically would therefore require that teachers who will impart these skills are trained in technical education. It was in realisation of this that the Nigerian government established colleges of education (technical) and state government established vocational and technical education department in the conventional colleges of education. Colleges of Education (Technical) is the unit of tertiary education saddled with the responsibility of training technical teachers to obtain non-degree but qualitative professional certificate in education (Olafare et al). The students in these colleges of education (technical) where technical education programmes are carried out are referred to as technical education students.

Furthermore, Boyi (2008) opined that the goal of colleges of education is to develop sellable skills in youths in order to make them useful to themselves, society and also become labour assets in the industry. Supporting the above view, Abdulkadir (2011), asserted that the major goals of colleges of education are to produce efficient and relevant craftsmen and women that will promote industrial development in the area of goods production, maintenance and general services. Therefore, colleges of education play a very vital role in the training and production of technicians for industries, imparting vital technical skills, helping towards the goal of self-employment and job creation and in the struggle towards technological advancement and acquisition (UNESCO 2012). The acquisition of practical skills in technical education requires the use of appropriate and latest method of teaching since it is activity base. This suggests that instructing students in technical education programme cannot be fully achieved without the use of student-oriented and activity-based instructional strategies. Henderson et al (2012) stated that significant empirical research has shown that students learning can be substantially improved when instructors move from traditional, transmission-style instruction to more student-centred, interactive instruction. In addition, Okwelle and Dokunbo (2018) also asserted that more interactional, alternative education methods lead to a higher level of school-to- real world transfer as evident in them. Therefore, it can be said that interactive and alternative learning methods such as field trip or instructional visit can be more beneficial to students' holistic learning than other day-to-day task in technical education.

One of the first and the most significant things that an educator and a technical educator should decide is the way of teaching that should be applied in the classroom. This is because the modus operandi employed by an educator has a huge impact on the learners. Amongst the various teaching methods, teachers seem to find the application of fieldtrip very challenging to use. Yet field trip

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seems to be the most appropriate for enhancing teaching and learning because of the various practical and hand-on activities that this learning method offers. Shakil et al (2011) defined field trip as a major source of providing knowledge to students by giving opportunity for self-experiences, observations and self-long, lasting learning. Similarly, Krakowka (2012) described field trip as a form of active learning and students get valuable experience when seeing things themselves. On the same note, Webster Dictionary (2022) viewed field trip as a visit to a factory, farm, or museum by students and a teacher for the purposes of firsthand observation. Therefore, field trip can be seen as an educational activity by a group of students or research workers, to study something first-hand in order to enhance learning.

Also, field trip can have a significant impact on the academic performance of students and in particular, technical education students. Abrami et al (2008) stated that field trip enhances critical thinking and problem-solving skills of students since field trip require students to think critically and solve problems in real life. Similarly, Nadelson and Jordan (2012) reported that field trips result in effective gains such as more positive feelings toward a topic. In like manner, Okwelle and Dokubo (2018) stated that field trips could be instructional trips (a visit by a class or group of classroom, designed to allow the students achieve specific course objectives); school contests or festivals (an extra campus activity, which provides an opportunity for students to demonstrate knowledge and skills developed through subject area instruction) ; and motivational trips (also an extra - campus activity, which is not a part of a scheduled class but provides a motivational incentive for school, club, group or class and is related to improving the school climate). Additionally, with field trip experience, students are able to access tools and environments that are not available at school, this is because the society is loaded with numerous learning laboratories. Field trips make it feasible to take technical students to visit various industries, workshops, building sites and so on. Each field trip experience solidifies the learning of technical students and supports important academic concepts (Zembazemba, 2019). Therefore, field trip happens to be one of the best teaching methods that most students always look forward to but instructors are not taking the advantage of it as provided in the Nigeria Certificate in Education Minimum Standard for Technical Education (2020) which states that Course Code TED 211 with Course Title "Foundry and Forging Work", one of the metalwork courses, students are expected to go on field trips and excursions to relevant industries which is compulsory. This shows that by design, every technical student should have gone for field trip or excursion at least once in order to have the experience before graduation as an NCE (Technical) graduate.

In this era of globalization, education is a primary need. Education gives us insight and also grooms the students' personality. Education is regarded as a promoter of human development and seen by many to be in the centre of all societal life and concern. (MoloKomphale & Mhlauli, 2014). Therefore, provision of quality education and training is the ultimate goal of any education system as it will reflect on the academic performance of students. The academic performance of the students is the key feature and the important goals of education (Navad & Abdullah, 2016). Sharma (2012) defined academic performance as how a student is accomplishing his or her tasks and studies. In the same vein, Okorie, (2014) described academic performance as the outcome of education as well as the extent to which the student, teacher or institution have achieved their educational goals. In the context of this study, academic performance is the end result of the efforts exerted by students. It represents outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person /students has accomplished specific goals.

Technical education is crucial to the technological development of any nation. Okwelle and Ojotule (2018) stated that no nation can develop to its fullest and keep pace with trends in science and technology without effective and efficient technical and vocational education and training (TVET).

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Field trip as a teaching method in technical education sparks students' interest in their academic endeavor. Hence, the utilization of field trip in teaching and learning of technical education will provide students with first hand practical experiences. It is in view of this that the researchers sought to investigate the impact of field trip on academic performance of technical education students in Colleges of Education(Technical) in South-South, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Although field trip is an important teaching and learning style, it seems as if many technical education teachers in the Colleges of Education in South-South Nigeria are not utilizing this teaching style effectively. Most of the technical education teachers in the Colleges of Education (Technical) in the South-South seem to only be utilizing very few fundamental teaching styles. Is it that the relevant industries are not available within the environment where most of these Colleges of Education (Technical) are located and where these students can go for such trips? Can it be that the management of such institutions may be afraid because of student's safety? Whatever be the case, in modern teaching, teachers are expected to be facilitators that promote self-learning and help students develop critical thinking skills and retain knowledge that leads to self-actualization. This can be best achieved when field trips are encouraged.

Unfortunately, without embarking on such an important part of learning process, it will be almost impossible for students to bridge the missing gap. It is against this backdrop that the impact of field trip on academic performance of technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South- South Nigeria becomes imperative.

The Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of field trip on academic performance of technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South- South Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- Determine the impact of field trip on the academic performance of technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria.
- Determine the quality of skills offered during field trips to technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria.
- Identify the challenges of technical education students undergoing field trip in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- What is the impact of field trip on the academic performance of technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria?
- What is the quality of skills offered during field trip to technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria?
- What are the challenges of technical education students undergoing field trips in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students on the impact of field trip on the academic performance of technical education of students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students on the quality of skills offered during field trip to technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria.

H03: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students on the challenges of technical education students undergoing field trip in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South Nigeria.

Methodology

The design adopted for this study was the survey research. It was carried out in south-south, Nigeria. A population of 190 was used for the study which comprised 91 lecturers and 99 students. In view of the manageable size of the population, the entire population was used as sample for the study. A 4 point rating scale questionnaire titled “Impact of Field Trip on Academic Performance of Technical Education Students Questionnaire (IFTAPTESQ)” was used to collect data from the respondents and the instrument was validated by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha (α) which yielded a coefficient of 0.9. Data collected was analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In taking decision, a mean rating of 2.50 and above was considered as accepted or agreed, while a mean rating of less than 2.50 was regarded as rejected or disagreed. In testing the hypotheses, the t-calculated was compared with the critical table, if the t-calculated was less than the t-critical, the null hypothesis was accepted and if the t-calculated was greater than the t-critical, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table1: Mean Rating on the impact of Field trip on Academic Performance of Technical Education Students.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Remark
1.	The use of field trips as supplementary method of teaching technical education motivates learners.	3.64	0.650	Agreed
2.	Field trip allows students to fully participate in the process of teaching and learning of technical education.	3.54	0.500	Agreed
3.	Field trip enhances team work in teaching technical education.	3.37	0.743	Agreed
4.	Field trip adds more skills, attitude and knowledge thereby enhancing teaching and learning.	3.50	0.640	Agreed
5.	Field trip allows students to relate with an expert therefore enhancing effective teaching and learning of technical education.	3.52	0.570	Agreed
6.	Students are able to see, feel, touch the objects taught in the classroom during field trip which enhances academic performance.	3.48	0.754	Agreed
7.	Field trip enables students to relate with other students from other schools which enhances effective teaching and learning.	3.30	0.769	Agreed
8.	Field trip stimulates creativity in students which enhances teaching and learning of technical education.	3.42	0.583	Agreed
9.	Field trip provides opportunities for direct observation and develops the skill for keen observation in students which impact on their academic performance.	3.52	0.532	Agreed
10.	Field trip generates and sustains students interest in the subject and help the students to develop interest in certain professions.	3.44	0.586	Agreed

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S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Remark
11.	Field trip helps students to explore independently and this increase academic performance in technical education.	3.44	0.586	Agreed
12.	Field trip gives students the opportunity to have first-hand experiences which enhances academic performance .	3.43	0.620	Agreed
13.	Field trip helps to develop the ability of obligation and this enhances students academic performance.	3.38	0.694	Agreed
14.	Field trip helps to carry out practical work in technical education which impacts on students academic performance.	3.44	0.686	Agreed
Grand		3.46	0.373	Agreed

The data in table 1 revealed that all the items had their mean scores above 2.50 with their corresponding standard deviations. This indicates that lecturers and students agreed to the fact that all the items on table 1 regarding field trip has impact on the academic performance of Technical Education on students.

Table 2: Mean Rating on the Quality of Skills Offered during field trip to Technical Education Students.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Remark
	Field trip provides students with quality skills such as:			
15.	Benchmarking	3.37	0.601	Agreed
16.	Team work skill	3.03	0.813	Agreed
17.	Budget planning	3.25	0.865	Agreed
18.	Critical thinking skill	3.33	0.690	Agreed
19.	Operational skill	3.46	0.596	Agreed
20.	Observation skill	3.64	0.533	Agreed
21.	Performance review skill	3.55	0.559	Agreed
22.	Problem solving skill	3.25	0.769	Agreed
23.	Quality assurance skill	3.32	0.733	Agreed
24.	Systematic scheduling skill	3.32	0.709	Agreed
25.	Task management skill	3.39	0.788	Agreed
26.	Creative skill	3.63	0.506	Agreed
27.	Inquiry skill	3.44	0.693	Agreed
28.	Fact finding skill.	3.43	0.653	Agreed
Grand		3.39	0.483	Agreed

Table 2 revealed that all the items had their mean score above 2.50 with their corresponding standard deviations. This indicates that lecturers and students agreed to the fact that all the items on table 2 are the quality skills that field trip provides to technical education students during field trip.

Table 3: Mean Rating on the Challenges Faced by Technical Education Students during field trip.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std Deviation	Remark
	Students who embark on fieldtrip are usually faced with:			
29.	Financial constraints	3.35	0.794	Agreed
30.	Limited time frame and schedule	3.12	0.672	Agreed

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31.	Security issues	3.44	0.731	Agreed
32.	Poor accessible roads	3.21	0.800	Agreed
33.	Poor planning and organisation by institution management	3.05	0.733	Agreed
34.	Poor planning on the part of students	3.02	0.720	Agreed
35.	Acceptability of the resource facility/organisation	3.29	0.630	Agreed
36.	Poor orientation to students by management	2.93	1.046	Agreed
37.	Teachers unfriendly attitude	2.83	0.865	Agreed
38.	Uncooperative attitude of the authorities of field trip sites.	3.04	0.825	Agreed
39.	Stereotyped practices in field trips.	3.09	0.808	Agreed
40.	Lack of parental support.	2.88	0.782	Agreed
41.	Perception of students towards monetary involvement	3.04	0.819	Agreed
42.	Perception of students towards field trips.	3.11	0.741	Agreed
		3.10	0.546	Agreed

Table 3 revealed that all the items had their mean score above 2.50 with their corresponding standard deviation. This indicates that lecturers and students agreed to the fact that all the items on table 3 are challenges faced by technical education students during field trip.

Table4: t-test Analysis on the Impact of Field trip on Academic Performance of Technical Education Students

Hypothesis One

Group	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-cal	t-crit	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	91	3.404	0.344	188	-1.6784	±1.973	0.0949	Not Significant
Students	99	3.50	0.391					

Table 4 above revealed that the t-calculated was less than the t-critical value at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis which stated that: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of lecturers and students on the impact of field trip on academic performance of technical education students in Colleges of education (Technical) in South-south Nigeria was therefore accepted with a decision of no significant different (NS).

Table 5: t-test Analysis on the Quality of Skills Offered to Technical Education Students during Field trip

Hypothesis Two

Group	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-cal	t-crit	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	91	3.267	0.511	188	0.4532	±1.973	0.6608	Not Significant
Students	99	3.495	0.431					

Table 5 above revealed that the t-calculated was less than the t-critical at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis which stated that: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of lecturers and students on the quality of skills offered during field trip to technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South –South, Nigeria was therefore accepted with a decision of no significant difference(NS).

Table 6: t-test Analysis on the Challenges faced by Technical Education Students during Field Trip

Hypothesis Three

Group	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-cal	t-crit	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	91	3.086	0.541	188	-0.293	±1.973	0.770	Not Significant
Students	99	3.110	0.554					

Table 6 above revealed that the t-calculated was less than the t-critical at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis which stated that: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lectures and students on the challenges of technical education students undergoing field trip in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South, Nigeria was accepted with a decision of no significant difference (NS).

Summary of Findings

1. Field trips impacted on the academic performance of technical education students. Lecturers and students did not differ in their opinion regarding the impact of field trips on academic performance.
2. Field trips offered quality skills to technical education students. Lecturers and students did not differ in their opinion regarding the quality of skills offered during field trips.
3. Technical education students face challenges during field trips. Lecturers and students did not differ in their opinion regarding the challenges technical education students face during field trips.

Discussion

The result of research question one as presented in table 1 revealed that field trip impacted on the academic performance of technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South, Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Olayinka et al (2022) who found that field trip has a positive and significant impact on the academic performance of biology students in senior secondary schools. In addition, Telima et al (2022) found that learning outside the classroom such as field trip, industrial trips enhanced students’ academic achievement.

The test of null hypothesis one revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and students on the impact of field trip on the academic performance of technical education students. To corroborate this finding, Buseretal (2019) reported that field trips increased students interest and motivation, leading to higher academic achievement. Similarly, this finding also confirms the result of Obiegbu and Anurudu (2020) which found that students who went on fieldtrips had higher achievement scores in geography than those who did not. The implication of the findings of hypothesis one is that field trip gives students access to first hand information about concepts and they are able to see for themselves how real some concepts are. This positively enhances the academic performance of technical education students.

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The result of research question two as presented in Table 2 revealed that field trip provides technical education students with quality skills. This finding is in consonance with the finding of Rodrigues and Ravasco (2021) which found that field trip facilitated and improved the quality of skills in students as well as enhanced their academic performance. In the same vein, Lee et al (2020) found that outdoor experimental learning such as fieldtrip had a positive impact on students' critical thinking skills.

The test of null hypothesis two revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and students regarding the quality of skills offered to technical education students during field trip. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Mahgoub and Alawad (2015) which found that there was a significant impact in the performance of students within the experimental group and that field trip fosters student creative thinking skills. This implies that field trip enhanced the creative skills of students which will in turn lead to increase in their academic performance.

The result of research three as presented in Table 3 revealed that technical education students undergoing field trip are faced with challenges. This finding aligns with the finding of Akpınar, et al (2012) which asserted that field trips has positive benefits for students' learning and motivation, but also has challenges such as safety concerns and logistical issues. In addition, Okwelle and Dokubo (2015) found that lack of students interest in outside classroom learning, unawareness of field trips benefits, teacher's unfriendly attitude, inability to prepare for fieldtrips, security fears and concern, lack of school administrators support, curriculum influence and time for field trips are the constraints on the utilization of field trip in technology education instructional delivery.

The test of hypothesis three revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and students regarding the challenges technical education students undergoing field trip face. This finding conforms with the study of Ngakhile (2017) which found that finance, teacher's incompetence, time frame, wrong perception about field trips as well as the nature of syllabus restricting the use of fieldtrip in teaching and learning of history at ordinary level.

Conclusion

The classroom is a limited environment, learning of technological courses must go beyond the four walls of the classroom. Field trips are crucial and vital for a quality technical education programme. Qualitative life long learning are derived from students who engage in field trip or industrial visits. Field trip offer an opportunity to motivate and connect students to appreciate and understand classroom concepts, which increases student's skills, knowledge foundation, promoting further learning and higher level thinking strategies despite the several challenges facing technical education student during field trip. Therefore, field trip has great potentials in enhancing the academic performance and providing quality skills for technical education students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in South-South, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. That government should improve on the amount of funds allocated to the education sector as undergoing field trip requires funding.
2. Regular and well planned field trips should be organized for technical education students so as to expose them to learning outside the classroom. This will enhance their academic performance.

3. Institutions should support field trip by providing vehicles and also creating an enabling environment for technical education students to undergo field trip.
4. Management of institutions should create more awareness about field trip so as to stir the involvement of technical education students.
5. Parents should support field trip visits by providing all the needed monetary needs for their wards (technical education students).

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